

Astrophysical neutrinos: current status and future prospects

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Neutrino astrophysics – the experimental landscape

Ackermann et al. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.08096>

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NOTE
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **BLUE** ARE COMPLETE OR UNDER CONSTRUCTION.
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **WHITE** ARE PROPOSED.

Esteban, Prohira, Beacom, Phys. Rev. D **106**, 023021

Simona Toscano, TeVPa'25

Neutrino production mechanics

Opening of the neutrino window...

Excess of neutrinos observed by IceCube in 2013 (HESE analysis)

→ opening of the neutrino window to the Universe

Fast forward 13 years..

What we know....

- Diffuse flux of extragalactic neutrinos confirmed by GVD
- Latest fit prefers broken power-law (4.7σ)
- Flavour: 1:1:1

Resolved neutrino sources

TXS 0506+056

- High energy IceCube track from 2017
- Location: known Blazar, TXS 0506+056 also 'flaring' in X-rays at the time.
- Extensive Multi-messenger follow-up
- ν burst in 2015

NGC 1068

- Excess of upgoing neutrino candidates from direction of an Active Galaxy
- 10 years of data
- Very few gamma rays

Galactic plane

- Diffuse / unresolved contribution from our Galaxy
- ~10% of all cosmic neutrinos

TXS 0506+056

290 TeV event on 22 September 2017

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.08816>

Search through historic data showed a neutrino flare at 4.1σ
 Index $\sim 2 - 2.1$ depending upon integration periods

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.08794>

NGC 1068

- 2011 – 2020: ~79 neutrino excess equating to 4.2σ
- Interestingly not particular ‘jet-dominated’
- evidence of emission from other sources

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2211.09972>

Galactic plane

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.04427>

All sky data from 10 years show a 4.5σ detection of neutrino emission from the galactic plane
Different models fit used in likelihood fit. Most significant fit was from π^0

Other neutrino events

$$E_{\mu} = 120^{+110}_{-60} \text{ PeV}$$

$$E_{\nu} = 220^{+570}_{-110} \text{ PeV}$$

KM3-230213A: interpretation

- Lucky to see this in first year of operation – tension will decrease
- Source not identified, cosmogenic?
- KM3NeT will recalibrate and improve the direction measurement

$\hat{\phi} = 7.5 \times 10^{-10} \text{ GeV cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$

experiment	data	expected
IceCube	0	0.6
Auger	0	0.4
KM3NeT	1	0.013

Aart Heijboer, TeVPA'25

Other neutrino events?

S33

R.J. Nichol / Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 626-627 (2011) S30-S35

A strong H-pol non-inverted signal seen!

- Expected background events: 4×10^{-4}
- 27.4 deg below horizon, $E = 0.6 \pm 0.4$ EeV

Direct Cosmic Rays

Reflected Cosmic Rays

NEW PHYSICS ?

Chord length: 5500-7000 km (20-30,000km water equivalent)
 1600km SM interaction length @ 1 EeV

Background estimate $< 10^{-2}$

R. Nichol, UCL

Diffuse UHE tau neutrino?

- ANITA I-IV flights 2006 through 2017
- A small number of small 'anomalous events' observed
- Detailed study showed a strong (2 flux orders of magnitude) tension between these events and fluxes seen by IceCube.

PHYS. REV. D 99, 063011 (2019)

Looking to the future

IceCube Gen2

- Increase optical volume by factor 8
- Multi-PMT DOMs
- Large Radio-array on top for UHE and CR physics

IceCube Upgrade

mDOM

D-Egg

- Precision oscillation measurements
- Improved detector calibration
- R&D for IceCube-Gen2

Dense and diverse new sensors;
Explore deep ice down to 2.6 km

Deploying now!

P-One

KM3NET

Two sites, one collaboration, one technology

Oscillation Research
with Cosmics In the Abyss

Astroparticle Research
with Cosmics In the Abyss

Letter of intent: J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys. 43 (2016) 084001

KM3NET

ARCA

ORCA

	ORCA	ARCA
String spacing	20 m	90 m
OM spacing	9 m	36 m
Instrumented mass	7 Mton	500*2 Mton
Operating today	33 lines	48 lines

Neon, HUNT, Trident...

Neon South China Sea
<https://arxiv.org/html/2408.05122v3>

HUNT, South China Sea/Lake Baikal
 ICRC '23 (1080)

Trident, South China Sea
Nature Astronomy 7, 1497 (2023)

Detector	Volume [km ³]	Number of Strings	Number of OMs	Type of OM
TRIDENT	7.5	1,211	24,000	31 × 3" PMTs & SiPM
HUNT	30	2,304	55,000	1 × 20" PMT
NEON	10	1,200	21,600	31 × 3" PMTs

Pushing the energy limits

PEUO

PUEO in Antarctica 2025

PUEO is Flying!

Already 20 days of flight

Instrument is working well being monitored by collaborators around the World

- 200k radio antennas over 200k km² : ~ 20 hotspots of 10k antennas at various favorable sites around the world
- Phased approach - Status at ICRC2025:
 - Prototype GRANDProto300 - 65 DUs deployed and running
 - First CR candidates
 - Finalizing GRANDProto300 within the next 3-years.

- 100-1000 stations with ~10 antennas each, viewing shower from top of mountain.
- Interferometer concept: clustered phased-array for triggering, and long-baselines for pointing.
- Prototype: 6 dual-polarized dipole + 4 scintillators for CR validation
- First CR candidates - A. Zeolla (BEACON coll.) PoS(ICRC2025)444

Trinity

- 18 air-shower Cherenkov telescopes (in 3 sites) optimized for detecting Earth-Skimming neutrinos in 10-1000 PeV range.
- Wide-FoV (60deg)
- Located at 2-3 km altitude
- 20% duty cycle compensated by detection of very distant showers (as far as 200 km)

TAMBO

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- 5000 water tanks deployed in slope
- characterization of astrophysical neutrino flux in 1-10 PeV range (ν_τ component)
- small tank separation (150m): low-energy threshold

S.Toscana, TevPA'26

Diffuse Flux, 1:1:1 Flavor Ratio

